

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

CORRELATION OF MILK YIELD AND TOTAL PROTEIN, ALBUMIN, GLOBULIN CONTENTS IN THE BLOOD SERUM OF FLECKVIEH, HOLSTEIN AND THREE-BREED COW GENOTYPES UPON THE ACCLIMATIZATION PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The research was performed at the age of 965 days at the first lactation of Holstein, Fleckvieh, three-genotype cows, and at 2060 days of age at 4 lactations of the same cows. The amount of milk on the 14th day of 5 months of 4 lactations was examined, and a blood sample was taken on the 15th day.

The correlation between total serum protein, albumin, globulin and daily milk intake was examined and the albumin / globulin ratio and the quantitative and qualitative indicators of milk production were determined, which determines the acclimatization process.

Keywords: Holstein, Fleckvieh, three-breed, serum, albumin, globulin.

Introduction

Cattle blood with its morphological and physicochemical properties is considered to be the result of a long-term biological evolution and addresses all changes taking place in the animal organism. The blood serum contains great amount of various proteins, the most essential of which are albumin, globulin and fibrinogen. Upon the method of proteins polymorphism (electrophoresis) it has been found out that in 3-18-month-old male and female animals of different genotypes the albumin content is reduced, while the globulin amount grows up [1].

Through the method of protein polymorphism, it has been identified that the albumin content against the total cattle protein amount (%) makes 40-48 % and globulin fractions are as follows: α -12-20%, β -16-21%, γ -20-30% [2].

Throughout the scientific research it has been disclosed that the factors affecting the quantity of the blood components are, for instance, feeding method, year season, productivity level, housing conditions, age, gender, physiological condition, acclimatization process, breed class, animal's individual properties and a number of other factors.

Materials and methods

The research was carried out in 2017, at "Arzni Poultry, Cattle and Pig-breeding Farm", OJSC, in the Kotayk region. Three groups of first lactation cows of different genotypes aged 965-day-old have been formed:

I group - Holstein purebred - 5 cattle heads

II group – Fleckvieh purebred - 5 cattle heads

III group -Three-cross/breed cattle: 25% Caucasian Brown Cattle x 25% Jersey Cattle x 50% Holstein Cattle (25% CB x 25%J x 50% H)- 5 cattle heads [3].

To evaluate the effect of age and acclimatization factors, 2060-day-old fourth lactation cows of the mentioned genotypes were selected and again three groups were formed:

I group – Holstein purebred - 5 cattle heads

II group – Fleckvieh purebred - 5 cattle heads

III group – Three-breed cattle: 25% Caucasian Brown Cattle x 25% Jersey Cattle x 50% Holstein Cattle (25% CB x 25%J x 50% H)- 5 cattle heads.

The I and IV lactations, milk yield and blood of the fifth month, as well as correlation of the daily milk yield and the total protein, albumin and globulin contents in the blood serum of the mentioned three genotypes have been investigated, besides, the correlation coefficient of the albumin/globulin has been determined, which sets up the acclimatization process.

The control computation of the daily milk yield amount was conducted on the 14th day of the 5th month for the first and fourth lactations, while the blood sampling was carried out on the 15th day. The cows were kept in the pasture of the "Arzni Poultry, Cattle and Pig-breeding Farm", OJSC, characterized by an exuberant summer vegetation cover situated in the subalpine zone of the Geghama mountain range at Abovyan province.

Through the indicators related to the correlative relationships between the amounts of total proteins and milk fat +milk protein the acclimatization process and further breeding issues of the investigated genotypes was described.

The research results concerning the changes in the blood serum indicators recorded in the 5th month of the first and fourth lactations in Holstein, Fleckvieh and three-cross cow breeds kept on the "Arzni Poultry, Cattle and Pig-breeding Farm", OJSC, are introduced in Table 1.

Table 1

Changes in the indicators of the blood plasma in the 5th month of the first and fourth lactations in the Holstein, Fleckvieh and three-breed cows*

Genotypes	Blood plasma indicators	Biometric indicators				
		n	Lim	M±m	σ	C _v
First lactation						
Holstein	Total proteins	5	7.13...7.42	7.31±0.05	0.11	1.50
Fleckvieh		5	7.01...7.35	7.20±0.06	0.14	1.94
Three-Breed		5	7.35...7.45	7.40±0.02-	0.04	0.54
Holstein	Albumin	5	3.02...3.28	3.10±0.05	0.11	3.55
Fleckvieh		5	2.73...3.07	2.96±0.07	0.16	5.41
Three-Breed		5	2.99...3.10	3.05±0.03	0.06	1.97
Holstein	Globulin	5	4.02...4.39	4.21±0.06	0.15	3.56
Fleckvieh		5	3.95...4.51	4.25±0.12	0.26	6.12
Three-breed		5	4.25...4.44	4.35±0.03	0.07	1.61
Fourth lactation						
Holstein	Total protein	5	7.22...7.43	7.34±0.05	0.10	1.36
Fleckvieh		5	7.02...7.21	7.13±0.03	0.08	1.12
Three-Breed		5	7.25...7.44	7.35±0.03	0.07	0.95
Holstein	Albumin	5	3.10...3.54	3.24±0.08	0.19	5.86
Fleckvieh		5	2.73...3.06	2.91±0.06	0.12	4.12
Three-Breed		5	2.82...3.20	3.06±0.07	0.16	5.23
Holstein	Globulin	5	3.60...4.31	4.05±0.12	0.27	6.67
Fleckvieh		5	4.10...4.48	4.22±0.08	0.17	4.03
Three-Breed		5	4.13...4.49	4.29±0.07	0.15	3.5

In the first lactation, cows of Fleckvieh genotype lag behind the three-breed cows in the blood protein content by 0.20 g/L, and the Holstein breed – by 0.11 g/L, while in terms of albumin content Holstein breed exceeds the three-breed by 0.05 g/L and Fleckvieh breed by 0.14 g/L [4].

Regarding the globulin content, the three-breed cows with 4.35 g/L index exceed the Holstein breed by 0.14 g/L and the Fleckvieh cows – by 0.10 g/L.

Variability coefficient of the albumin content in Fleckvieh breed for the first lactation makes Cv=5.41 %, while that of the three-breed cows is 1.97 %, which testifies about the uniformity of the three-breed cows.

In the fourth lactation, the three-breed cows exceed the Holstein ones in the blood protein amount by 0.01 g/L and the Fleckvieh cows – by 0.22 g/L, while in respect with globulin content, the highest index has been recorded in the three-breed genotypes (4.29 g/L), whereby exceeding the Holstein cows by 0.24 g/L, while the Fleckvieh breed – by 0.07 g/L.

The highest albumin content has been observed in Holstein cows (3.24 g/L), thus, exceeding the Fleckvieh breed by 0.33 g/L and the three-breed cows – by 0.18 g/L.

As compared to the first lactation the globulin content in the fourth lactation has decreased in the Holstein cows by 0.16 g/L, in Fleckvieh breed – by 0.03 g/L and in three-breed cows – by 0.06 g/L.

In the fourth lactation the highest variability coefficient for the albumin content has been recorded in Holstein breed - Cv=5,86 %, which surpasses the index

of three-breed cows by 0.63 % and the Fleckvieh cows – by 1.74 %.

Thus, through the data analysis of the blood albumin amount, it becomes clear, that along with age index its amount declines and this fluctuations are within the limits of biological reliability.

According to the biological description, in the first lactation the variation coefficient of the total proteins in the Fleckvieh cows makes Cv=1,94 %, and in the fourth lactation it is 1.36 % in the Holstein breed[4].

The data on the indices of milk fat + milk protein as the main breeding property are introduced in Table 2, according to which the highest index in the first lactation with the value of 359 kg is observed in the Holstein breed, which exceeds the same index of Fleckvieh breed by 37.9 kg and the three-breed cows – by 33.3 kg.

The values for the milk fat + milk protein amounts evidence that the cows of the discussed three genotypes demonstrate superiority over the indices of the first lactation cows by 83.9 kg, 45.5 kg and 44.8 kg for the Holstein, Fleckvieh and three-breed cows respectively.

Regarding the indices of the daily milk yield, the cows of all three genotypes in the fourth lactation surpass the mentioned index of the first-calf cows, which is viewed as a regular phenomenon.

The data of Table 2 indicate, that with regard to 305-day milk yield, the cows of Holstein breed in the fourth lactation surpass that of the first lactation by 1127 kg or 18.26 %, the surplus against the Fleckvieh breed makes 573 kg or 11.5 % and against the three-breed cows it amounts to 642 kg or 13.1 %.

Table 2

Milk productivity indices of the cows of Holstein, Fleckvieh and three-breed genotype in the first and fourth lactations *

Genotypes	Indicators	Biometric indicators				
		n	Lim	M±m	σ	C _v
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
First lactation						
Holstein	Daily milk yield, kg	5	23...27	25.2±0.66	1.48	5.87
Fleckvieh		5	16...24	19.2±1.46	3.27	17.03
Three-Breed		5	15...21	18.4±0.98	2.19	11.90
Holstein	Milk yield for 305 day, kg	5	5011...5069	5042±11.38	25.44	0.50
Fleckvieh		5	4397...4516	4448±21.3	47.63	1.07
Three-Breed		5	4230...4364	4285±21.73	48.58	1.13
Holstein	Milk fat content, %	5	3.8...3.9	3.86±0.02	0.05	1.30
Fleckvieh		5	3.9...4.1	3.98±0.04	0.08	2.01
Three-Breed		5	4.1...4.2	4.16±0.02	0.05	1.2
Holstein	Milk protein content,%	5	3.2...3.3	3.26±0.02	0.05	1.53
Fleckvieh		5	3.2...3.3	3.24±0.02	0.05	1.54
Three-Breed		5	3.4...3.5	3.44±0.02	0.05	1.45
Holstein	Milk fat, kg	5	190.4...197.7	194.6±1.67	3.72	1.91
Fleckvieh		5	174.6...180.3	177.0±0.94	2.11	1.19
Three-Breed		5	173.4...179.8	178.3±1.23	2.74	1.54
Holstein	Milk protein, kg	5	160.4...167.3	164.4±1.60	3.57	2.17
Fleckvieh		5	141.4...146.4	144.1±0.85	1.91	1.33
Three-Breed		5	143.8...149.8	147.4±1.20	2.69	1.82
Holstein	Milk fat+ milk protein, kg	5	363.9...350.8	359±3.26	7.29	2.03
Fleckvieh		5	317.8...325.4	321.1±1.52	3.39	1.06
Three-Breed		5	317.3...329.6	325.7±2.26	5.04	1.55
Fourth lactation						
Holstein	Daily milk yield, kg	5	29...38	33.8±1.83	4.09	12.1
Fleckvieh		5	19...22	20.6±0.68	1.52	7.38
Three-Breed		5	15...23	18.8±1.36	3.03	16.12
Holstein	Milk yield for 305 day, kg	5	6018...6265	6169±44.67	99.88	1.62
Fleckvieh		5	5012...5032	5021±3.49	7.80	0.16
Three-Breed		5	4863...5016	4927±24.78	55.41	1.12
Holstein	Milk fat content, %	5	3.8...4.0	3.88±0.04	0.08	2.06
Fleckvieh		5	3.9...4.1	4.0±0.03	0.07	1.75
Three-Breed		5	4.1...4.2	4.18±0.02	0.04	0.96
Holstein	Milk protein content,%	5	3.2...3.4	3.3±0.03	0.07	2.12
Fleckvieh		5	3.2...3.4	3.3±0.03	0.07	2.12
Three-Breed		5	3.3...3.4	3.34±0.02	0.05	1.5
Holstein	Milk fat, kg	5	232.8...244.3	239.3±2.0	4.48	1.87
Fleckvieh		5	195.7...205.5	200.9±1.56	3.48	1.73
Three-Breed		5	199.4...210.7	206±1.83	4.09	1.99
Holstein	Milk protein, kg	5	199.7...206.7	203.5±1.21	2.70	1.33
Fleckvieh		5	160.6...170.6	165.7±1.59	3.55	2.14
Three-Breed		5	162.2...167.5	164.5±1.03	2.30	1.40
Holstein	Milk fat + milk protein, kg	5	434.9...451.1	442.9±3.05	6.82	1.54
Fleckvieh		5	356.3...371.4	366.6±2.72	6.09	1.66
Three-Breed		5	364.7...376.2	370.5±2.11	4.72	1.27

So, it is obvious, that the milk productivity growth is also related to acclimatization factor, which is proved upon the fluctuating coefficient of albumin/globulin (0.68-0.74) ratio [5].

Table 3

The correlative relationships between the daily milk yield and indices of blood serum proteins in the first and fourth lactations of the cows of Holstein, Fleckvieh and three-breed genotypes

Genotypes	Indicators	Correlative relationships (r) and regression (R) coefficients		
		R	R _{1/2}	R _{2/1}
1	2	3	4	5
First lactation				
Holstein	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	0,97	13,03	0,07
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	0,69	0,07	6,85
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	0,04	0,003	0,54
Fleckvieh	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	0,84	0,04	19,52
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	0,54	0,04	6,76
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	-0,13	-0,006	-2,65
Three-Breed	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	0,87	0,02	47,73
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	-0,62	-0,02	-19,52
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	0,65	0,02	23,83
Fourth lactation				
Holstein	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	0,98	39,89	0,02
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	0,04	0,66	0,003
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	0,38	0,98	0,02
Fleckvieh	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	0,92	17,54	0,05
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	0,79	7,06	0,09
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	-0,51	-6,41	-0,04
Three-Breed	Between the daily milk yield and total blood proteins	1,0	43,19	0,02
	Between the daily milk yield and globulin	-0,007	-0,14	-0,0004
	Between the daily milk yield and albumin	0,46	8,64	0,02

The data of Table 3 testify that the correlation coefficient between the daily milk yield and total blood protein in the first lactation of the Holstein cow breed makes $r=0,97$, while in the fourth lactation it is $r=0,98$, which validates the best course of acclimatization upon the respective values of 0.84 and 0.92 in Fleckvieh breed and 0.87 and 1.0 in three-breed cows.

Thus, since the three-breed cows have 25 % blood content from Caucasian Brown cow breed, they adapt best to the technological housing conditions of the farm cows.

So, albumin/globulin coefficient in the first lactation makes 0.73 in the Holstein cows, 0.69 in the Fleckvieh genotype cows, while in the three-breed cows it is 0.70. In the fourth lactation this coefficient makes 0.8, 0.68 and 0.71 respectively.

Conclusion

1. Regarding the total protein content, the cows of Fleckvieh breed in the first lactation stand behind the Holstein cow breed by 0.11 g/L and the three-breed cows – by 0.20 g/L. In the fourth lactation they lag behind the Holstein cows and three-breed ones by 0.21 g/L and 0.22 g/L respectively.

2. In the first lactation, the Holstein breed exceeds the three-breed cows in albumin content by 0.05 g/L and the same index of Fleckvieh breed – by 0.14 g/L.

3. In the fourth lactation the globulin amount in the Holstein cows declines by 0.16 g/L, as compared to the first lactation and in Fleckvieh cows it is decreased by 0.03 g/L, while in the three-breed cows it demonstrates growth by 0.06 g/L.

4. The increase of the milk yield amount in the fourth lactation testifies that the growth of milk productivity is also related to the acclimatization, which is

proved by the albumin/globulin correlation coefficient fluctuating within the range of 0.68-0.74.

5. So, the correlation coefficient of the daily milk yield and the total protein blood protein has been identified, which makes $r=0,97$ in the first lactation of the Holstein breed and in the fourth lactation it is $r=0,98$, in the Fleckvieh breed these indices are 0.84 and 0.92 and in the cows of three-breed genotype they are 0.87 and 1.0 respectively. The data of the milk yield amount evidence about the best course of the acclimatization process.

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